

Fabrication and characterization of silicon nanowires

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Abstract— In this project work, Silicon nanowires were fabricated on the Si substrate by aqueous method. In this aqueous method Ag is used for electroless chemical etching. The precursors those were taken are AgNO₃, HF and H₂O₂. Si nanowires are fabricated at 55°C. The samples were characterized by X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscope. Result shows morphology of the Si nanowires by scanning electron microscope. X-ray diffraction confirms the phase Si. The XRD analysis confirms the phase of silicon and crystalline nature of silicon. It is found to be single crystalline with plane (1 0 0). The SEM study shows that the particles were uniform and afterwards the non uniformity arises. At 60 second of electroless deposition, the particles shape became anisotropic. Some of the particles have grown vertically. This kind of non uniform pattern can cause a non uniform distribution of Silicon nanowires. It is confirmed that the morphology of the nanowires also depends on the resistivity of the wafers. The magnified HRTEM image shows the well-resolved lattice spacing of the silicon nanowire, which depicts the crystalline nature of the silicon nanowire.

Keywords— silicon, nanowires, fabrication, anisotropic, aqueous method

I. INTRODUCTION

In the last years, there is an increasing demand of nanomaterials. Nanomaterials are in the form of nanoparticles, nanowires, nanotubes. The rising demand is because of its properties. Nanowires are also called as quantum wires because of its dimension. Nanowires are of the diameter nanometers range and length in the range of micrometers. Recently, there is an increase in growing interest in the research work on Si nanowires because of its application in many fields like optoelectronics, sensor field, and photovoltaic applications. If Si nanowires can be used properly in photovoltaic cells then it will be more efficient and can help in solving the energy crisis. Transformation of bulk material to ductile material can be done by the creation of dislocation and fostering dislocation motion at high temperatures of about $2/3^{\text{rd}}$ of melting point of bulk or phase transformation at high pressure [1]. Understanding the atomic mechanisms and dynamics of a brittle material impacted by an external force is fundamentally important to theoretical and applied physics, such as atomic lattice elastic-plastic response, brittle-ductile (B-D) transition materials toughness, hardness, and fractures. Currently, with the emergence of new directions in flexible dimensionality of electronic devices and forms as well as advancements in single nanowire (NW) electronics, it has become crucial to assess the nanoscale mechanical responses such as elastic-plastic deformation of the most important semiconductor materials, such as Si and SiC [2]. Theoretical study reveals that recent developments in simulation techniques have opened new approaches for investigating the microscopic origins of complex nanomaterial phenomena. However, some results are contradictory too i.e. brittle-fracture features with small strain were observed by large atomic number molecular dynamics (MD) simulations for SiC NWs[3]. On a contrary to that large strain elasticity and ductile fractures were achieved. Yet, the important thing is experimental evidence which is mandatory to clarify the true deformation features and mechanisms of the ceramic nanowires. Any small change in the local environment, such as perturbations in forces, pressure or mass, can be detected by monitoring the corresponding changes in the resonance frequency of the NWs. This technique of nanowire-based NEMS has been successfully applied in atomic force microscopy (AFM) and various kinds of sensors and actuators. There are many semiconductor material systems which would be suitable for fabrication of nanowire field-effect sensors. Quite a few have been demonstrated successfully, including silicon, silicon-germanium, indium oxide, tin oxide, galliumnitride, among others, and yet silicon stands out as a clear favorite for the very same reason that the microprocessors in our computers are crafted from silicon: microfabrication[4].

Silicon has proved over and over again to be a practical and versatile material for electronic devices. It does not have the high mobility or direct band-gap of III-V compound semiconductors but it can be grown cheaply, has a stable oxide, has reliable etchants, allows for good control over electronic properties and can be fabricated on scale of very-large wafers. Even in our own lab, we tried several other material systems and growth methods before settling on silicon as our material of choice. Advances in the design, synthesis and characterization of nano-materials are expected to provide the unprecedented ability to manipulate matter at the most fundamental level, allowing the implementation of novel nanometer scale devices and systems with unique properties and of utmost technological importance. Bottom-up growth has enabled researchers to demonstrate a myriad of nanostructures of various material compositions and geometries. However, it remains a challenge to turn some of these materials, which are admittedly exciting and beautiful, into robust device technologies. Ultimately, nature seems to favor bottom up organization and thus it is certainly a useful and noble task to pursue. By using top down fabrication, on the other hand, the semiconductor industry has demonstrated the ability to create billions of nanostructures on a single square centimeter of silicon. In the rush to produce exciting end results, the details are lost and ultimately the results are less understandable and less compelling. In the case of bio-sensing, where we must combine aspects of solid-state device physics and electrical engineering with chemistry, biochemistry, and fluid mechanics it is difficult for one individual to be fully versed in all the details. And yet to fully understand and appreciate the complexity of the operation of nanowire sensors, it is important to have a detailed understanding of the solid-state physics, chemistry, and mechanics that combine to produce a measurable effect [5]. Prior to the industrial revolution, the world population growth and natural resource consumption were relatively insignificant compared to what they are today. This started to change with the invention of the steam engine and continued with the development of the internal combustion engine. These engines allowed society to transport and move goods efficiently around the world, sparking the future for rapid technological development and consumption of our natural resources [6]. Again in the mid-twentieth century, society hit another monumental landmark with the invention of the transistor. Since then, the number of transistors on an integrated circuit has been growing at an exponential rate, almost doubling every two years. This has led technology to grow at an unprecedented rate. Developed countries are continuing to make technology faster, cheaper and smaller, allowing individuals to consume more than ever. At the same time, modern technology is becoming available to non-developed countries, who can now gain access to electricity and health care, drastically improving their quality of life and life expectancy, resulting in a rapid increase in the population of the world. The combination of the rapid population growth and increased power consumption has had a severe impact on the pollution of our planet and the depletion of our natural resources. In order to further mitigate these risks, society needs to adopt clean energy technologies to replace the technologies consuming our natural resources while still meeting the demands from society [7].

The demand to improve efficiency in current systems is also highly desired. Thermoelectric devices, which are solid-state energy harvesting devices capable of converting a temperature gradient into an electrical voltage, offer the potential to achieve this goal. Currently, heat engines are used to produce ~90% of the world's energy in a useful form, of which ~60% is lost to the environment as waste heat, opening up promising opportunities for thermoelectric devices [8]. For example, a typical automobile has an efficiency of 20-25% due to the production of waste heat, of which the majority is expelled in the exhaust and radiator [9]. The waste heat from the exhaust or radiator could be harvested with a thermoelectric device to convert this energy back into useful electricity, which would reduce the mechanical load placed on the alternator and increase the overall engine efficiency. The gas mileage would increase, allowing automobiles to be manufactured with smaller engines that would require less power. Thermoelectrics have

characteristic traits that make them promising in many applications. For example, typical heat engines become less efficient as they are scaled down, while thermoelectric devices maintain a relatively stable efficiency over a wider range of power generation levels, opening up opportunities for thermoelectrics in low power (< 1 kW) applications [10]. Figure 1-1a shows a representative illustration of the low power regime where the thermoelectric efficiency is more efficient than conventional heat engines [11]. The range of power levels where thermoelectrics are more efficient will only increase as the efficiency of thermoelectric materials continues to improve. Furthermore, the demand for systems capable of supplying small amounts of power is becoming more important as technology is allowing devices to decrease in size and increase in performance. In addition, most of these applications require the devices to be wireless, portable, and long lasting: this mandates an onboard power source since they can no longer rely on power from the grid. While batteries are typically used in such applications, there are two major drawbacks: batteries (1) contain toxic materials and (2) need to be replaced. On the other hand, thermoelectric devices can harvest waste heat from their surrounding environment without a finite energy density, large components, and noise since they possess no moving parts [12]. These characteristic traits have allowed thermoelectrics to be used in some maintenance-free applications for up to 20 years or more, even under extreme conditions with very little performance degradation [13]. With current performance and cost, the primary applications for thermoelectric devices are for space exploration and wireless devices in harsh and dangerous environments where the benefits outweigh the current cost and performance limitation. It is unlikely that thermoelectric devices will soon become cost-effective and efficient enough to compete with conventional large scale heat engines. However, if the material cost, manufacturing and integration technologies can be substantially improved, then thermoelectric devices could harvest the ~60% heat lost from conventional heat engines. With future improvements in the efficiency and cost, thermoelectrics can become commonly used energy harvesting devices, capable of powering a variety of applications such as implantable biomedical devices, remote sensors in hard to access locations, personal hand held electronics, and hybrid conventional heat engines.

II. EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Aqueous method (electroless chemical etching)

Fabrication of nanowires takes place after having several continuous reaction in the aqueous solution so it is called as aqueous method. Most commonly for the etching method the elements that are used for deposition are Ag, Au, and Cu on Si substrate. These metals attract the electron from the Si substrate. Oxidation of Si takes place [43]. In one way to prepare Si nanowires by this method AgNO₃/HF solution is taken. Si wafer is dipped in the solution for the deposition. In the solution there are plenty of Ag⁺ to oxidize Si by take electron from it and also produces SiO₂. In the presence of HF, SiO₂ gets easily etched away. Si under Ag particles are protected. Then by using HNO₃, Ag particles are removed by leaving Si nanowires.

The reactions that are taking place in the solution of AgNO₃/HF are as follows:

Fabrication of silicon nanowires

In this project work the fabrication of Si nanowires by aqueous method (electroless chemical etching) is adopted. The materials/chemicals are used here are Si wafer, HF, AgNO₃ and H₂O₂.

At first the cleaning process is done. The substrate is taken and dipped properly in the deionized water. Then the wafer is cleaned with isopropanol alcohol. After it is cleaned with isopropanol alcohol wafer is again cleaned with 5% of HF. All these cleaning process was done to remove dust, organic, and other contaminants. After the substrate cleaning was done the glass beakers and the Teflon that were used in the fabrication method were cleaned thoroughly. 3.4 gm of AgNO_3 was mixed in 80 ml of water and 20ml of HF was added. Then the Si wafer was dipped in it for 3s and then removed. Same procedure was followed with other Si wafers.

A mixture of 20 ml of HF, 78 ml of water was prepared. To this 2ml of H_2O_2 was mixed and kept in a plastic bottle. In a small piece of Si wafers in a Teflon jig and kept inside the bottle. Then the bottle was kept in the oven in 55°C . Aqueous solution of 10% of HNO_3 water was prepared. After the sample was removed from the oven it was kept in the prepared HNO_3 solution. The shape and morphology of particles are studied by SEM pictures obtained. Whether the particles have attended the nano range is studied by taking the TEM pictures of sample which gives the sharp peaks in XRD analysis.

III. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

I. Scanning electron microscopy (SEM)

Silver (Ag) particles were deposited prior to the fabrication of silicon nanowires. The resistivity of the (100) silicon substrate was 1-10 ohm.cm. The thickness of the substrates was $\sim 500\ \mu\text{m}$. The shapes of the Ag particles were varied with electroless deposition time as shown in the figure. At the initial stage the particles were uniform and afterwards the nonuniformity arised. At 60 second of electroless deposition, the particles shape became anisotropic. Some of the particles have grown vertically. This kind of non uniform pattern can cause a nonuniform distribution of Silicon nanowires. Therefore, the particles grown for less time are comparatively uniform and suitable for Silicon nanowires growth.

Fig. 1. SEM Images of silver particles grown on silicon substrate (a) 2 s, (b) 5 s, (c) 15 s, (d) 30 s, (e) 45 s and (f) 60 s.

A growth time of 2s is preferred, where the average particle sizes were around 50-120 nm. **Fabrication of silicon nanowires:**The silver particle present on the silicon substrate (1-10 ohm.cm) locally oxidizes the silicon surface by electronic transport. During the HF treatment, the locally oxidized surface etched away to produce local pits. With the increase in etching time the depth of the pit increases. As a result, the smooth surface of the parent silicon wafer becomes nonuniform. As the Ag nanoparticles were very close to each other, the distance between the pits also in nanometer range. Therefore, the non-etched area stands vertically and can be considered as nanowires. The nanowire length depends on the etching time. The nanowires length increases with increase in etching time. The width of the nanowires were around 100-200 nm and length was around 20 μm for an etching of 20 mins. The aspect ratio of the nanowires was more than 100. However, the diameter of the nanowires was not uniform, which may be due to the nonuniform diameter of the silver particles.

Fig.2. SEM Images of Silicon nanowires at (a) 600 and 3000 magnification

Fig.3. SEM Images of Silicon nanowires at 7500

The above process is repeated for heavily born doped silicon substrate (resistivity ~ 0.001 ohm.cm), where no formation of the nanowires were found. It is confirmed that the the morphology of the nanowires also depends on the resistivity of the wafers.

II. X-Ray Diffraction: From the figure the XRD patterns taken by the XRD machine model number (Pan analytical, Xpert Pro) are matched with the JCPDS File and recognized as Silicon. The XRD analysis confirms the phase of silicon and its crystallinity. It is found to be single crystalline with plane (1 0 0).

(Fig.4. XRD result of silicon)

III. Transmission Electron Microscopy(TEM)

Fig.5.HRTEM image of Silicon nanowires

The HRTEM image of Silicon nanowires is shown in the figure 5. The magnified HRTEM image clearly shows the well-resolved lattice spacing of the silicon nanowire, which depicts the crystalline nature of the silicon nanowire.

IV. CONCLUSIONS

Zinc Si nanowires were fabricated on the Si substrate by aqueous method. In this aqueous method Ag is used for electroless chemical etching. The precursors those were taken are AgNO_3 , HF and H_2O_2 . Si nanowires are fabricated at 55°C . The samples were characterized by X-ray diffraction and scanning electron microscope. The XRD analysis confirms the phase of silicon and crystallinity nature of silicon. It is found to be single crystalline with plane (1 0 0). The SEM study shows that the particles were uniform and afterwards the non-uniformity arises. At 60 second of electroless deposition, the particles shape became anisotropic. Some of the particles have grown vertically. This kind of non-uniform pattern can cause a nonuniform distribution of Silicon nanowires. It is confirmed that the morphology of the nanowires also depends on the resistivity of the wafers. The magnified HRTEM image shows the well-resolved lattice spacing of the silicon nanowire, which depicts the crystalline nature of the silicon nanowire. The preceding chapters have laid out the promises and challenges underlying the synthesis, integration, and characterization of Si NWs (and semiconductor NWs in general). The versatility of VLS growth is embodied in the use of Pt and Au catalysts, the novel synthesis of nanotrees using migration of the catalyst material, and the fabrication of electrically conductive Si nanobeams through the epitaxial growth of NWs that bridge two distinct electrodes. Block copolymer templating of NW growth catalyst seeds and ex situ boron doping are demonstrated as promising aids in epitaxial NW device integration, while Raman spectrometry provides an encouraging alternative way to measure critical NW thermal properties. Numerous directions to pursue in continued research could be envisioned, but here only two will be presented.

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